

<i>He does not come here</i>	<i>avan ingu varukirathillai</i>
<i>She did not come yesterday</i>	<i>aval nettu varavillai</i>
<i>I do not know French</i>	<i>enakku French theriyathu</i>

In the case of the sentences used by the modal verbs, the word not is put in between the auxiliary verb and the main verb.

<i>He cannot swim</i>	<i>avanaal neentha mudiyathu</i>
<i>You should not come with us</i>	<i>nee enkaludan varakoodathu</i>
<i>He must not attend the party</i>	<i>antha virunthil avan kalanthukolla mattan</i>

Generally the morpheme *illai* is used to form the negative in Tamil. However, the morphemes *eithu*, *ain* are often used for the purpose.

English has some negative words they are also used to form the negation. Some are *barely*, *rarely*, *scarcely* and *seldom*. Though Tamil has no such words, the negative word *illai* is used to form the sentences. For example,

<i>I rarely ate in restaurants.</i>	<i>naan unnavu viduthiel chappittathillai</i>
<i>We seldom go out.</i>	<i>naankal veliya selvathillai</i>
<i>I scarcely know him</i>	<i>enakku avalai theriyathu</i>

Going to the difference in the structural patterns of the two languages the learner in the bilingual situation, for example, Tamil learner of English is faced by several difficulties in order to help him overcome these. An analysis of the frequently committed errors in the structural patterns becomes necessary.

Thus, the Tamil learners of English who are familiar with the roles of morphemes in constructing the interrogative and negative structures and the absence of inversion in the interrogative structures should look at the formation of those structures in English in a completely different perspective. The most of the mistakes that occur in the formation of those structures are made by the fundamental misunderstanding of the functioning of English. As there is the vast difference between English and Tamil in the formation of those structures, the mistakes happen very commonly, even in the script of a topper of the class, irrespective of the syllabus he or she studies. The functions of the modal verbs and the splitting of the main verbs into the auxiliary verb and the main verb have become a challenging task for the second language learners.

If one stands rigid on the perception he has without being objective, it is neither easy to communicate with the receiver nor to learn anything from him. If he goes into the shoes of the receiver to know the secret of his heart, even the efforts are needless; the similar kind of learning is needed in the language learning. It always happens with ease. In fact, learning the language is a pleasant and enjoyable activity if the learner acclimatizes himself sufficiently for the new language, like his natural learning of the first language. The rest is much easier.

References:

1. Bright, J. A., and Mc Gregor, G. P. (1970), Teaching English as a Second Language. London: Longman Group Limited.
2. Close, R. A. (1962), English as a Foreign Language. London, George Aillen A Unwin.
3. Hamby, A. S. (1992), Oxford Advanced Learners Dictionary of Current English. (4th ed.). London, OUP.
4. Littlewood, William T. Foreign and Second Language Learning. Cambridge: Cambridge UP, 1998.
5. Mullick, Ratna and Shefali Ghosh (1993), Ennilin Lan non Teachin From Then to Practice. Calcutta: Spectnim.
6. Palmer, Frank. (1984), Grammar. 2nd ed. London: Penguin.
7. Spolsky, Bemard (1972), "Attitudinal Aspects of Second Language Learning". Teaching English as a Second Language. Ed. Allen and Campbell. New Delhi: Tata Mcgraw-Hill Publishing Company Ltd., 401-412.
8. Verghese, Paul C. (1989), Teaching English as a Second Language. Delhi: Sterling.